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Self-mixing interferometry laser scanning imaging system for industrial quality control

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1 **Abstract**

2 Product quality inspection is a critical manufacturing step in industry, especially when it comes to serial
3 production. Typical optical quality inspection methods, however, rely heavily on the ambient lighting
4 conditions to function. Moreover, the regions of interest during inspection are often limited by the
5 predefined Field-of-Views (FOVs) and magnifications. We hereby introduce a laser diode scanning imaging
6 system with strong stray-light resistance (240,000 lumen/m²) and dynamic FOVs/magnification (1× to 5×).
7 By capturing the self-mixing interference power fluctuation of a laser diode and reconstructing a digital
8 image from a raster-scanning pattern, we deliver an open-architecture (non-proprietary hard/firm/software)
9 imaging system, built within a budget of \$1,000. Optical metrology trials were conducted, and revealing
10 that a spatial resolution of 20 microns and a measurement error rate of 2.23% have been achieved. A series
11 of validation tests suggest that our system has the potential to be used for quality inspection in the
12 manufacturing sector.

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14

15 **Introduction**

16 Automated and precise defect detection is crucial in industrial production to uphold product quality and
17 boost efficiency [1-3]. Non-contact and non-destructive quality inspection systems have become
18 increasingly popular within the industry [4,5]. Recent advancements in deep learning and high-performance
19 technologies have propelled machine vision systems that utilize sensitive sensors, such as CCD cameras,
20 to the forefront of this evolution [6-8]. Other camera-based methods considered to be promising include
21 structured light detection [9], terahertz imaging [10,11], and laser triangulation [12,13]. While these
22 techniques offer advantages in accuracy and real-time performance, they also encounter challenges such as
23 dependence on ambient lighting, vulnerability to stray light interference, complexity, compatibility with
24 existing machining equipment, and user-friendliness [14-16].

25 In contrast, detection technologies based on the self-mixing effect present significant advantages,
26 particularly regarding precision, reduced complexity, and resilience to ambient light interference [17,18].
27 Notably, terahertz imaging systems utilizing self-mixing interference have attracted attention due to their
28 high resolution, sensitivity, and noise resistance [19,20]. Different from camera-based type, these terahertz
29 imaging systems can leverage a single laser to serve both as the excitation source and sensor, simplifying
30 the composition design. However, current self-mixing terahertz imaging systems still face challenges in
31 industrial implementation. For example, some require the detection target to move in a specific orientation
32 perpendicular to the optical path for effective raster scan, which leads to several limitations [21,22]: (1)
33 Mechanical displacement can introduce noise; (2) Strict positioning requirements complicate their use in
34 typical industrial settings; (3) The detection speed may fall short of the demands of high-throughput
35 operations.

36 More importantly, these above current attempts do not exhibit their dynamic Fields-of-Views (FOVs)
37 capabilities, which can provide in-depth observation of the region of interest to obtain more information.
38 In summary, these limitations restrict their widespread adoption in industrial environments, confining their
39 use primarily to laboratory research and specialized applications.

40 The self-mixing interference phenomenon can be observed in any type of laser, with laser diodes offering
41 distinct advantages due to their affordability and versatility. Numerous studies suggest that the self-mixing
42 effect from low-cost laser diodes holds significant potential for various industrial measurement applications,
43 including displacement, velocity, vibration, and material properties [23-27]. The industrial application of

44 laser diodes often capitalizes on their high-frequency, high-speed, stable, and low-noise scanning
45 capabilities, achieved through components like galvanometers or polygon mirrors. Therefore, developing a
46 scanning imaging system that integrates laser diodes with self-mixing effects could effectively address the
47 limitations of current terahertz imaging systems. While some research has examined imaging systems based
48 on laser diodes, these studies have primarily focused on indirect understanding of target features, and
49 generally required complex parallel or confocal optical paths [28,29]. To date, no research has successfully
50 produced detailed scanning images comparable or better to those generated by terahertz systems.

51 This study introduces a novel scanning imaging system based on planar laser diodes self-mixing
52 interferometry, achieving low-noise and high-resolution imaging by raster-scanning. Designed with
53 streamlined and interchangeable components within a budget of \$1,000, it has volume advantages and
54 ensures high compatibility with existing industrial facilities. This system has been proved that can
55 effectively mitigate the stray light with a brightness density of 240,000 lumen/m², and allows for dynamic
56 FOVs (magnification 1× to 5×) when conduct in-depth observation to areas of interest without losing
57 resolution. And a series of optical trials have proved that the system can achieve a spatial resolution of 20
58 microns and a measurement error rate of 2.23%. In addition, the profile identification and defect detection
59 methods designed in conjunction with the system showed an error rate of only 0.4% for standard blocks
60 with a machining error of ±0.4 μm. The anticipated outcomes of this system include advancements and new
61 insights into intelligent industrial quality inspection and control, providing a cost-effective and user-friendly
62 solution.

63

64 **Results**

65 **Self-mixing interferometry laser scanning imaging system**

66 The self-mixing interferometry laser scanning imaging system was designed for simplicity and open-source,
67 with detailed specifications for all components provided in Supplementary Table S1. The composition and
68 operational logic of the system are illustrated in Fig. 1. During the scanning process, a data logger
69 continuously collects data, which is automatically uploaded to PC software to generate a 2D bitmap upon
70 completion. This streamlined procedure allows for one-click operation.

71 The experimental prototype, depicted in Fig. 1a, represents the fundamental hardware configuration of the
72 system. Laser self-mixing interference serves as the fundamental principle behind the scanning prototype
73 utilizing laser diodes to capture the characteristics of scanned targets and provide feedback output [17]. In
74 the proposed prototype, the laser diode is both the source and the detector. Its LD pins are connected to a
75 power supply circuit that ensures stable output through a current source, while its PD pin is connected
76 through a series of resistors, allowing the data logger to record the resulting terminal voltage. The laser
77 light emitted by the diode reflects off the scanned object, generating self-mixing interference within the
78 internal cavity. As the scanning target varies, the feedback optical power of the laser diode adjusts
79 accordingly, which is reflected in the PD pin's terminal voltage. A detailed explanation of the scanning
80 detection method based on laser self-mixing interferometry is provided in Supplementary Note 1.

81 In terms of the optical path, a series of lenses and a focuser are used to realize conventional functions such
82 as collimation, expansion, contraction, shaping and dynamic focusing of the laser beam. A galvanometer is
83 configured at the end of the optical path to guide the laser beam to the scanning area. The galvanometer
84 receives analog signals from a controller to execute a defined scanning strategy, with a scanning distance
85 set at 200 mm, suitable for most applications. As illustrated in Fig. 1b, the scanning strategy employs a
86 raster-scanning pattern composed of multiple scan lines. In each scanning cycle, the laser beam transitions
87 to the next line via horizontal fly-back after completing each line in the X direction, continuing until all
88 lines in the Y direction are scanned. It is worth noting that the feedback signal generated by the step of
89 jumping from one scanning line to another will be avoided and will not participate in the final imaging data.
90 The scanning area is defined as 50 mm × 50 mm, consisting of 1,000 scan lines in the Y direction, with
91 each line containing 1,000 scanning points. Consequently, for the scanning array, the point spacing in both
92 X and Y directions is set at 0.05 mm. With a scanning frequency and data sampling rate of 83.3 kHz, a

93 complete scanning cycle takes approximately 12 seconds, significantly exceeding the capabilities of
94 existing terahertz imaging technologies [19-21]. This frequency is the optimal operating frequency for the
95 system at the current stage, and as discussed in Supplementary Note 12, there is room for improvement.
96 The system is designed for simultaneous scanning and data logging (Fig. 1c), and upon completion, a
97 bitmap is automatically generated within 1 second (Fig. 1d,e), and saved to the specified path.

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99

100 **Fig. 1 | Schematic diagram of the configuration of the proposed laser scanning imaging system.** **a** The laser diode acts as
 101 both the signal source and the detector, and its internal photodiode inputs the detected scanning features into the data logger in
 102 the form of analogue signals. **b** All scans are performed with the laser focused on the scanning substrate, and the parts are placed
 103 directly on the substrate, which can be set as required. A raster-scanning pattern was set as scan strategy. **c** The microprocessor
 104 used performs analogue-to-digital conversion of the signal and imports the data string into the PC software after collecting
 105 enough number of analog signal values. **d** A series of python codes convert the data string into a 2D matrix and draws the bitmap
 106 using OpenCV functions. **e** The bitmap shown here was obtained from the scan of a metal gear sample.

Laser beam spot characterization

The knife-edge method [30,31] was employed to measure the beam spot size of the scanning laser across different areas within the entire scanning range, evaluating its calibration effectiveness. Detailed information regarding the experimental design is provided in Supplementary Note 2. For reference, Fig. 2a shows the laser beam profile measured by the CCD sensor, showing that $D4\sigma_X$ and $D4\sigma_Y$ are 0.208 mm and 0.214 mm respectively. The laser beam spot has been shaped to be nearly circular and has a uniform intensity distribution, demonstrating high quality. Experimental results summarizing the detected spot size of the laser in various scanning areas are presented in Supplementary Table S2 and illustrated in Fig. 2b. The findings indicate that, using the CCD sensor as a benchmark, the fluctuation in the beam spot size of the scanning laser within the whole scanning field range varies from 0.52% to 7.92%. This suggests that the optical path design of the system effectively maintains a reliable beam spot shape during scanning.

119 **Metrological capability**

120 Details regarding the metrological measurement accuracy experiment are provided in Supplementary Note
 121 3, which involved benchmarking against a standard block with a machining error of $\pm 0.4 \mu\text{m}$. All
 122 experimental data are compiled in Supplementary Table S3, with error rate data further illustrated in Fig.
 123 2c. The results indicate that the measurement error rate of the imaging system ranges between 1.43% and
 124 2.33%, supporting the conclusion that the proposed imaging system possesses reliable metrological
 125 capabilities. The results from both the spot characterization and measurement accuracy experiments
 126 demonstrate that the system's reliability is maintained within the scanning area. This reliability is essential
 127 for the subsequent application of the imaging system in defect detection for scanned components.

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129

130 **Fig. 2** | **a** Beam profile property of the scanning laser in the system, which is measured by a commercial CCD sensor. **b** The
131 experimental results of investigating the beam spot size by knife-edge method. **c** The experimental results of determining the
132 measurement accuracy of system by benchmarking with a standard block. **d** The bitmap obtained by scanning the mica sheet,
133 which shows its surface texture, and a schematic of typical grey distribution. Higher grayscale values represent higher feedback
134 optical power. **e** The bitmap obtained by scanning the black cloth. **f** Histogram analysis of the bitmap of the entire and the selected
135 area of the mica sheet. **g** Shows the image generated by extracting a data string with 1,000 values from the centre of the mica
136 sheet scan data, and its curve fitting. **h** Shows the change in feedback signal intensity during 1D scanning. **i** and **j** These two
137 schematic diagrams show the light recovery difference of the system when scanning at a small and large angle.

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Feedback optical power intensity characteristics during scanning

An inherent phenomenon of central overexposure in the bitmaps generated by the system is characterized, reflecting the feedback optical power intensity characteristics during the scanning process. This study utilized two primary types of scanning substrates to enhance imaging quality for various scanned parts. As illustrated in Fig. 2, the bitmap obtained from scanning black cloth displays a uniform grayscale distribution (Fig. 2e), whereas the bitmap from the mica sheet exhibits a central overexposure (Fig. 2d). This discrepancy arises from the differing reflectivity of the materials. Analysis of the original digital signal data from scanning the black cloth reveals that the intensity baseline of the laser feedback signal remains consistently low across the scanning area, leading to a uniform and featureless bitmap. In contrast, the mica sheet, with its high reflectivity and uniform surface, effectively reflects intensity variations of the laser feedback signal during scanning. The data string A-B extracted along the center of the image is plotted in Fig. 2g, fitting a cosine curve. This indicates that the intensity of the self-mixing interference signal varies in a cosine pattern with respect to the scanning angle [32,33], as shown in Fig. 2h. When the scan approaches the central area, the intensity of the laser feedback signal gradually increases, resulting in higher grayscale values, as depicted in Fig. 2f, i, and j.

Based on these findings, the periodic variation characteristics of the feedback optical power within the system can be derived. According to the three-mirror model in the self-mixing framework [18,34], the feedback parameter C is contingent upon the amount of light reflected back to the laser, which can be expressed mathematically in Eq. (1).

$$C = \frac{\tau_{ext}}{\tau_l} k_{ext} \sqrt{1 + \alpha^2} \quad (1)$$

where τ_l is the round-trip time for light in the laser cavity.

In the formula, k_{ext} is the coupling coefficient that depends on the reflectivity of the exit laser facet and the reflectivity of the target, via Eq. (2), resulting the difference between scanning mica sheet and black cloth.

$$k_{ext} = \varepsilon \sqrt{\frac{R_{ext}}{R_s}} (1 - R_s) \quad (2)$$

where, R_s and R_{ext} are the reflectivity of the emitting facet of the laser and of the external target, respectively, and ε is the fraction of the reflected light coupled back coherently into the lasing mode [18].

164 Further, Eq. (3) is used to obtain the change in emitted optical power or laser terminal voltage, either of
165 which can be used as the observable self-mixing signal. The threshold gain change Δg_{th} will lead to a
166 proportional shift in optical power.

$$\Delta g_{th} = -\frac{k_{ext}}{L} \cos\phi \quad (3)$$

167 where, L is the distance from the laser to the target.

168 Therefore the change in optical power can be written as

$$\Delta P = \beta \cos(\phi) \quad (4)$$

169 where β defines the observable self-mixing signal amplitude, which depends on a number of laser and
170 system parameters such as the amount of light being coupled back into the laser cavity, the distance to the
171 target, and the photon lifetime in the laser cavity.

172 Next, the relationship between the external phase change and the target displacement distance can be written
173 as

$$\phi_0(t_n) = \frac{4\pi\nu_0}{c} [L_0 + d(t_n)] \quad (5)$$

174 where c denotes the speed of light in vacuum.

175 In the proposed system, due to the fixed scanning frequency, the change in target displacement actually
176 presents a harmonic motion displacement with an amplitude A and frequency f over time, as

$$d(t_n) = A \cos(2\pi f t_n) \quad (6)$$

177 Therefore, it can be finally considered that in the proposed scanning system, when other system parameters
178 are determined, the change of optical power in the period presents the relationship shown in Eq. (7).

$$\Delta P \propto \cos^2(t_n) \quad (7)$$

179 And based on this relationship, curve fitting was successfully performed, as shown in Fig. 2g. This is
180 considered to be the theoretical basis of the central exposure phenomenon of the proposed system. And it
181 is expected that in the future, that law can be used to strip the feature from the acquired data to achieve
182 uniform feedback signal intensity, and uniform pixel base of the image.

183 **Stray light resistance**

184 Fig. 3 presents the physical images of all scanned samples (Supplementary Note 7) in this study, along with
185 the corresponding generated bitmaps. Notably, all bitmaps produced by the proposed imaging system were
186 captured without any image post-processing, and have the same resolution of $1,000 \times 1,000$ pixels.

187 As comparison, under typical imaging conditions (adequate indoor lighting), the scanning imaging results
188 for components such as gears, directed energy deposition (DED) parts, and heat sinks are illustrated in Fig.
189 3a. The bitmap precisely and clearly displays the profile details of the scanned gear, including each
190 individual tooth. For the DED parts, the system accurately reveals every structural layer on the surface, and
191 captures all features about manufacturing defects as well. The heat sink, characterized by its complex multi-
192 layer thin-walled structure, is also depicted with rich detail in the bitmap.

193 To evaluate the imaging performance of the system under challenging conditions, two scenarios were
194 designed: one in complete darkness and the other illuminated by a strong flashlight ($240,000 \text{ lumen/m}^2$,
195 which far exceeds the industrial limit of 500 lumen/m^2). Specific design strategies for these tests are detailed
196 in the Supplementary Videos and Supplementary Note 5. As shown in Fig. 3b-d, the result demonstrates
197 that the system operates normally in dark environments, confirming its capability of imaging without
198 ambient light. Additionally, to assess the impact of light pollution, a strong flashlight was introduced
199 midway through the scanning process, as shown in Fig. 3e-g. Consequently, half of the bitmap shown in
200 Fig. 3h was generated under strong flash conditions. Importantly, no distinct features emerged between the
201 upper and lower sections of the same bitmap, indicating that the imaging performance remains unaffected
202 by adding strong external light.

203 These two experiments unequivocally demonstrate that the system resists any variations of ambient lighting
204 conditions. This aligns with a key advantage of laser self-mixing interference systems, as noted in
205 Supplementary Note 1: their self-coherent nature effectively suppresses most external radiation that does
206 not originate from within the laser cavity [17]. Furthermore, the constantly rotating galvanometer mirror
207 minimizes the likelihood of external light entering the internal laser cavity through the reverse optical path.

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210 **Fig. 3 | Investigating the imaging capabilities of the proposed system under various conditions. (all displayed bitmaps**
 211 **have the same resolution of 1,000×1,000 pixels). The scale bar is 10 mm. a** Three representative parts (gear, additive
 212 **manufactured DED-DirectEnergyDeposition part, and metal heat sink) were imaged using a conventional system configuration**
 213 **with adequate room lighting and a mica sheet as the substrate. b-d** Imaging parts under various special conditions, including
 214 **complete darkness, using different laser sources, and using different scanning substrates. e-g** Schematic diagram of adding strong
 215 **flash interference when scanning is halfway through. h** The Bitmap generated after the entire scanning process does not contain
 216 **traces of strong flash interference that are sufficient to observe.**

217

Dynamic Field-of-Views (FOVs)

The concept of investigating the system's ability on FOVs is presented in Supplementary Note 6 and Fig. S4. The ability to customize the FOVs of the proposed scanning imaging system allows zooming in to any location within the scanning area at different magnifications. This magnified imaging is achieved by compressing the scan step length, by adjusting the scan parameters. Notably, magnified imaging retain the same resolution of $1,000 \times 1,000$ pixels, enabling the capture of intricate local details.

The current design allows the system to achieve a dynamic FOVs between $1 \times$ and $5 \times$ magnification, corresponding to a scanning area of $50 \text{ mm} \times 50 \text{ mm}$ to $10 \text{ mm} \times 10 \text{ mm}$. As shown in Fig. 4a, the PCB was imaged at a series of magnifications within the mentioned magnification range without sacrificing resolution. In order to objectively quantify the image quality of this series of bitmaps, we used the two image quality analysis tools Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) and Entropy introduced in Supplementary Note 7. The specific operations and calculation results are shown in Supplementary Table S4 and plotted in Fig. 4b. It can be seen that compared with the original observation magnification, the bitmaps obtained under different magnifications show better SNR. As for Entropy, from the data performance, it can be concluded that such magnified observation does not weaken any image information.

Further intuitively demonstrate the system zoom-in imaging brings richer information or higher quality imaging of specific areas of interest. In Fig. 4c, after imaging the coin at $3.50 \times$ magnification, rich manufacturing details and defects on its surface can be captured, which are difficult to identify in the original magnification imaging bitmap. Fig. 4d-g shows an imaging study of an electronic chip, calculating and comparing the SNR and Entropy values of the bitmaps obtained by full scan and partial scan, respectively. The specific operations and results are shown in Supplementary Table S5 and further plotted as Fig. 4h. It can be seen that in terms of SNR and Entropy, for the same region of interest, the evaluation value of the independent partial scan image is almost twice that of the full scan image. Higher information entropy and SNR indicates that the partial scan image has higher quality, more information and more complex details, which is more conducive to important analysis and decision-making. This is also reflected in the actual image content: a parameter mark on the top of a capacitor ("100" / "50V") - imperceptible in the full scan (Fig. 4f) - becomes clearly visible upon zooming in (Fig. 4g).

246
 247 **Fig. 4 | Dynamic FOVs ability of the proposed system. (all displayed bitmaps have the same resolution of 1,000×1,000**
 248 **pixels). The scale bar is 10 mm. a** By adjusting only the scan code, independent scanning of the specified area of interest on
 249 the PCB board within the magnification range of 1.00×~5.00× is achieved. **b** The SNR and Entropy tools were used to analyse
 250 the bitmaps obtained by independently scanning the PCB board at five different magnifications. **c** Scan the coin with dynamic
 251 FOVs to observe the rich processing details and defects on its surface. **d-e** The red framed area indicates that the chip has been
 252 fully scanned and a bitmap has been generated. **f** Cut out the specified area from the full scan bitmap. **g** The bitmap generated
 253 by partial scan, with the perceptible parameters label on the top of a capacitor ("100" / "50V"). **h** The SNR and Entropy tools
 254 were used to perform quality analysis on images **f** and **g**. **i** Micron-scale defects on a PCB board were characterized using optical
 255 microscopy and showed structural sizes of 20-50 microns. **j** Defects on the PCB board surface were identified by the system,
 256 and their existence can also be seen at the fitting processed data string extracted along A-A'.

Micron-level spatial resolution

Fig. 4i,j showcase the system's ability to characterize micron-level structures with the flexible FOVs. Subtle defects on the PCB surface are clearly displayed in the generated bitmap, with further optical microscopy confirming that these structures range from 20 to 50 microns in size. This result demonstrates that the proposed system has the capability to identify micron-scale defects even in the most basic imaging configuration. Notably, a 20-micron defect can be identified although using a laser source with a beam spot size of approximately 200 microns, thanks to the phase differences created during the interference process [29,35]. It can be concluded that the proposed system achieves a spatial resolution of 20 microns under the current basic configuration. Supplementary Note 8 discusses the theoretical foundations for the horizontal resolution achievable by the proposed system. This resolution is sufficient for routine industrial product quality inspection and is expected to improve further with optimizations to the optical path and the monitoring laser diode.

Usability in industrial quality inspection and control

To evaluate the prototype's feasibility for industrial part quality control, a method was developed for profile identification and defect detection, as detailed in Supplementary Note 9. This novel method is supported by the system's concise feedback signal format. It involves hundreds of lines of python codes that read the bitmap of the scanned part alongside the corresponding model file, enabling automatic calculation of machining errors based on the machining model. As illustrated in Supplementary Fig. S5, this method achieves an error rate as low as 0.4% in benchmarking tests based on standard blocks, which can be considered to be the inherent error rate of the proposed system. This result demonstrates that the proposed method effectively enables the system to accurately detect machining defects.

Fig. 5 showcases the results of profile recognition and defect detection for a specific target metal part. By comparing the scanned bitmap with the processing model, the proposed method successfully identified three significant defects of the part, with the coordinates marked in green color. Additionally, based on Eq. (S15), the calculated machining error rate for this part is further determined to be 1.83%, which has the potential for providing a basis for assessing the degree of machining error.

Building on this method, the proposed system aims to facilitate intelligent decision-making for part quality inspection on production lines, as depicted in Fig. 5g. Specifically, after scanning the part and analyzing it with the model file for machining, the system automatically determines, magnifies, images, and archives the defective areas. Its ability to customize the FOVs while maintaining high resolution enhances this process. Recording defects for all scanned parts allows for the identification and mitigation of potential processing issues. The severity of the processing error, based on the calculated error rate, will guide the subsequent actions after evaluation. If the error exceeds allowable limits, the system triggers an alert to decide whether to discard or repair the part.

This entire process can be executed with just a few dozen lines of Python code, thanks to the system's straightforward data acquisition and processing design. Therefore, this intelligent decision-making process can be set up to be automatic after the scan is completed. The key advantage lies in the construction of the bitmap from digital signals, which allows for more direct and efficient closed-loop feedback control. This approach is more efficient, simpler, and cost-effective compared to camera-based solutions and visual recognition algorithms [36,37].

Fig. 5 | Proposed profile identification and defects detection method for supporting the imaging system. **a** The physical metal part with machining errors. **b** The generated bitmap for this metal part. **c** Using a dozen of Python codes to realize bitmap binarization and contour identification. **d** A reference contour was extracted from the machining model file of this metal part. **e** Defect area determination based on python codes by comparing with model files, and during that process, the machining error rate was calculated to be 1.83%. **f** Subtracting background for better showing defect detection results. **g** Details of three significant defects on the part profile are shown. **h** Intelligent decision-making process developed for supporting the proposed system.

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308 **Discussion**

309 In summary, we have successfully developed a high-resolution scanning imaging system based on self-
310 mixing interferometry using laser diodes. The system is proposed to supplement the limitations of current
311 attempts, such as poor compatibility, heavy reliance on ambient lighting conditions, complex composition,
312 high cost, and inability to customize the field of view.

313 This system is constructed with conventional and simplified hardware and software, avoiding custom
314 components that could weaken the repeatability. This study only demonstrates the basic imaging
315 configuration of the system, and the hardware and software can be improved or replaced to any degrees as
316 needed. Designed for compatibility, portability, and scalability (Supplementary Note 11), the system is cost-
317 effective, built within a budget of \$1,000 (Supplementary Table S1).

318 The imaging results of a variety of parts demonstrate that the system can accurately display profiles, surface
319 textures, and identify micron-level defects. The principle of self-mixing interferometry provides a 20
320 micron spatial resolution for the system. Benchmarking against standard block has confirmed the system's
321 precision metrology capabilities, showing an error rate lower than 2.23%, and facilitating profile
322 identification and defect detection through straightforward code instructions. Its customizable FOVs allows
323 for dynamic and detailed observation ($1\times$ to $5\times$ magnification), providing more detailed information, which
324 is a feature not commonly found in current attempts. Besides, the system has been demonstrated to have
325 the potential to perform 3D reconstruction of inspected parts (Supplementary Note 10 and Fig. S6). These
326 capabilities support an integrated intelligent decision-making process, underscoring the proposed versatile
327 system's potential applications in industrial quality control.

328 The coherent detection characteristics of the system ensure that its imaging performance remains unaffected
329 by ambient lighting conditions. Especially the resistance to stray light ($240,000$ lumen/m²), which far
330 exceeds the industrial limit (500 lumen/m²). This advantage positions the system as a preferred choice in
331 specialized environments, such as dark settings or areas with unavoidable light pollution, including
332 unmanned factories or in-situ machining monitoring based on high-energy beam. Consequently, the system
333 excels in scenarios where other sensor-based solutions struggle due to lighting requirements. This feature
334 also enhances compatibility with machine vision solutions that demand high image clarity and purity,
335 aligning with current technological trends.

336 In addition, the special mechanism of the system was modelled, characterized and discussed, that is, the
337 inherent difference between bright and dark fields caused by the special feedback light power variation
338 characteristics. This is one of the current limitations of the system (Supplementary Note 12) and is expected
339 to be removed in the next stage. Other limitations include the need to improve the system's scanning strategy
340 and optical components to achieve a comprehensive upgrade in speed, workspace, and imaging quality in
341 the future.

342 In conclusion, the system has been developed with a focus on cost-effectiveness, compactness, scalability,
343 high-precision detection, user-friendliness, and intelligent decision-making in industrial production. This
344 novel system is expected to provide alternative solutions and valuable insights into the field of industrial
345 quality inspection.

346

347 **Methods**

348 **Data logging and bitmap generation**

349 The data logging and bitmap generation processes are all based on known and open-source technology, as
350 illustrated in Fig. 1c,d, along with Supplementary Fig. S8. The data logger utilized in this study is the fully
351 open-source Arduino DUE board. It reads the analog voltage signal generated by the photodiode within the
352 laser diode and converts it into the corresponding digital signal. The data acquisition frequency is set at
353 83.3 kHz, matching the scanning frequency. Upon completion of the scan, the data logger collects $1,000 \times$
354 $1,000$ voltage values, resulting in a total of 1,000,000 terminal voltage values formatted as a long data string.
355 These values are then imported into PC software, specifically Python scripts, via a communication port. To
356 facilitate processing, the voltage values, initially ranging from 0 to 3.3 volts, are expanded to a range of 0
357 to 255 (gray values) with minimal precision loss. Subsequently, the code organizes these values into a two-
358 dimensional array of dimensions $1,000 \times 1,000$. Finally, this two-dimensional array is converted into a
359 grayscale bitmap using the OpenCV library.

361 **Scanning laser beam spot characterization method**

362 Knife-edge method was conducted for characterizing the beam spot size of the laser during scanning
363 through the whole area, and a commercial CCD sensor was set for providing reference. Detailed
364 information is provided in Supplementary Note 2.

366 **Metrological capability investigation method**

367 A method was proposed for investigating the metrological capability of the proposed system. Detailed
368 information is provided in Supplementary Note 3.

370 **Image quality evaluation tools**

371 This study involved the use of the SNR tool and Entropy tool, details of which are provided in
372 Supplementary Note 7.

374 **Profile identification and defect detection method**

375 For supporting the proposed system, a novel method was developed for part profile identification and defect
376 detection. Detailed information is provided in Supplementary Note 9.

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378 **3D reconstruction method**

379 For supporting the proposed system, 3D reconstruction method was developed. Detailed information is
380 provided in Supplementary Note 10.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the Hong Kong Research Grants Council (Early Career Scheme Ref. No. 24220422, Ref. No. 14211623 and C4074-22G), and the CUHK Start-Up Fund (Ref. No. MAEG5501517)

Author contributions

H.W. and Z.S. conceived the study. Z.S. and F.L. designed and built the optical system. Z.S. designed and performed all of the experiments and characterizations. Z.S., F.L., Y.F.T., and A.M. prepared experimental materials. Z.S. prepared the figures and schemes. Z.S. prepared the original manuscript with revisions from H.W. and W.H.L.

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